

4-Sulpho-2-Aminobenzenethiol—A New Reagent for Gravimetric Determination of Mercury(II)

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4-Sulpho-2-aminobenzenethiol as a ligand has been used in the gravimetric determination of 6-30 mg Hg(II). The greenish yellow precipitate, $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{O}_3\text{NS}_2)_2$, is quantitatively precipitated in the pH range 2.0-6.0, adjusted with aqueous ammonia, and is weighed as such after drying at 105-110°. Interferences by Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , As^{3+} , Sb^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Tl^+ , Pd^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , UO_2^{2+} , MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} , Be^{2+} and Mg^{2+} could be overcome by using suitable masking agent. F^- , PO_4^{3-} , ASO_4^{2-} , tartarate, citrate and oxalate do not interfere. The standard deviation is $\pm 0.30\%$.

LITERATURE survey of important gravimetric methods¹⁻⁷ for the estimation of Hg(II) with organic reagents indicates that the procedures have either poor selectivity and sensitivity or cover narrow pH range. In this communication we recommend a new reagent, 4-sulpho-2-aminobenzenethiol⁸ which reacts with mercury(II) quantitatively in the pH range 2.0-6.0 forming a greenish yellow thermally stable complex $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{O}_3\text{NS}_2)_2$. The reagent is almost selective for Hg(II). The procedure covers a wide pH range and is successfully applicable in the determination of Hg(II) in the presence of sulphide forming metal ions.

Experimental

Preparation of the reagent: Freshly distilled 2-aminobenzenethiol (20 ml) was added dropwise into cooled sulphuric acid (sp. gr. 1.84). The reaction mixture was stirred mechanically and maintained at 5°. The stirring was continued for another 30 min after the complete addition of the thiol. The mixture turned light pink in colour and a thick mass was obtained. The cooled product was slowly added to 200 ml of ice-water with stirring until effervescence ceased. The faint yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with ice cold water and recrystallised twice from water. The colourless needle-shaped crystals were dried over calcium chloride, m.p. 190°, yield 80% (Found: C, 34.4; N, 6.30; Calcd.: C, 35.12; N, 6.82%).

Mercury(II) solution: Mercury(II) nitrate (E. Merck) in 0.1M nitric acid was standardized gravimetrically.

Diverse ions: Solutions of other ions were prepared from chloride or nitrate salts of the cations and sodium, potassium and ammonium salts of the anions.

Apparatus: A Cambridge pH meter was used for pH measurements.

General procedure: An aliquot of standard solution containing 6.0 mg to 30.0 mg of Hg(II) is diluted to 150 ml with distilled water and the pH adjusted at 3.0-4.0 with sodium acetate solution. The mixture is then heated to 80° on a water bath and two to three fold excess of the reagent, taken in 10-20 ml of ethanol, is added with stirring. The greenish-yellow precipitate formed is digested on a boiling water bath for 15 min with occasional stirring. The precipitate is then collected on weighed gooch-crucible (No. 3) washed with hot water followed by 20% ethanol and dried at 105-110°. The metal content of the complex is determined using a factor 0.3296. The results of several determinations of Hg(II) are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF MERCURY(II)

Hg taken(mg)	Weight of the complex (mg)	Hg found (mg)	Relative error%
6.03	18.20 ; 18.25	5.99 ; 6.01	-0.66 ; -0.33
11.71	35.40 ; 35.63	11.66 ; 11.74	-0.42 ; +0.25
29.80	90.00 ; 90.60	29.66 ; 29.86	-0.47 ; +0.20

Procedure in presence of diverse ions. A known volume of mercury(II) and foreign anion or cation and 1.0-1.5 g of suitable masking agent were diluted to 200 ml and mercury(II) was determined following the general procedure. Table 2 records the results.

Results and Discussion

Properties and composition of the complex: The yellowish-green mercury(II)-4-sulpho-2-aminobenzenethiol complex melted with decomposition at 152 ± 1 . The complex was insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in ethanol, methanol, benzene, acetone, ether and chloroform. The mercury(II)-complex was analysed for its carbon, hydrogen and

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TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF MERCURY(II) FROM DIVERSE IONS (Hg taken : 11.22 mg)

Diverse ions added (mg)	Masking agent	Weight of the complex (mg)	Mercury found (mg)	Relative error%
Tartarate (1500)	—	34.04	11.21	-0.08
Citrate (1000)	—	34.01	11.20	-0.16
Oxalate (1000)	—	34.6	11.22	00
Fluoride (500)	—	34.10	11.23	+0.08
Phosphate (100)	—	34.05	11.23	00
Borate (100)	—	34.00	11.20	-0.16
Arsenate (100)	—	33.90	11.20	-0.16
Tl ⁺ (50)	Tartarate	33.88	11.19	-0.24
Al ³⁺ (50)	Tartarate	34.05	11.22	00
Cr ³⁺ (50)	Tartarate	34.02	11.21	-0.08
Mg ²⁺ (50)	Tartarate	34.01	11.20	-0.16
Zn ²⁺ (50)	Tartarate	34.08	11.23	+0.08
Cd ²⁺ (50)	Tartarate	34.03	11.21	-0.08
As ³⁺ (50)	Tartarate	34.18	11.25	+0.24
Sb ³⁺ (50)	Tartarate	34.14	11.24	+0.16
Bi ³⁺ (50)	Tartarate	34.20	11.26	+0.32
MoO ₄ ²⁻ (50)	Tartarate	34.04	11.21	-0.08
WO ₄ ²⁻ (50)	Tartarate	33.95	11.19	-0.24
UO ₂ ²⁺ (50)	Ammonium acetate	33.90	11.17	-0.40
Be ²⁺ (50)	NH ₄ HF ₂	34.08	11.23	+0.08
Fe ²⁺ (50)	"	34.02	11.21	-0.08
Mn ²⁺ (50)	Citrate	33.89	11.20	-0.16
Co ²⁺ (50)	"	33.90	11.20	-0.16
Ni ²⁺ (50)	"	34.15	11.25	+0.24
Cu ²⁺ (50)	"	34.00	11.20	-0.16
Pb ²⁺ (50)	"	34.25	11.28	+0.48
Pd ²⁺ (50)	"	34.28	11.29	+0.56

nitrogen content to determine its composition. The composition of the complex corresponds to the

formula $Hg(C_6H_6O_8NS)_2$ in which mercury to ligand ratio was 1 : 2 (Found : C, 23.30 ; N, 4.68. Calcd. : C, 23.66 ; N, 4.60%).

Effect of pH and reagent concentration : Experimental studies showed that precipitation of mercury(II) commenced at pH 1.5 and was complete in the range 2.0-6.0. Precipitation of mercury(II) was carried out between pH 3.0 to 4.0 and it was observed that 2-3 times the theoretical quantity of the reagent was necessary for complete precipitation. Higher reagent concentration resulted in co-precipitation of the reagent.

Interferences : Di-sodium-EDTA and silver(I) interfered with the determination of mercury(II).

Precision and accuracy : The relative standard deviation for 25 determinations of mercury(II) was $\pm 0.30\%$.

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